

PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING THE DUAL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE TRAINING OF SPECIALIST PERSONNEL IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM.

Nusratov Anvar Nematjonovich

Doctor of philosophy (PhD) in pedagogical sciences, associate professor:

Isoqova Shaxnoza Shuxrat qizi

Graduate student of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology of Asia International University:

Abstract: in this article, we aim to create wide opportunities for training middle-level personnel with qualified and modern professional skills in all areas of the economy, and to support the interests of young people in acquiring professions and specialties.

Key words: Dual education system, One-to-one reference, Orientation to practice, Distance education, Individual completion,

The main part: by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 29, 2021, the regulation on the procedure for organizing dual education in the professional education system was approved. Based on the regulation, this educational experience is being used today. The dual education system is a type of specialized education that provides the student with the opportunity to acquire theoretical knowledge in an educational institution, and practical skills directly at the workplace, that is, in the organization. The main goal of dual education is to prepare students for the quality of professional training.

Pedagogical foundations in the dual education system are very important in the training of specialists. These basics include:

1. One-on-one reference: Through one-on-one reference, professionals can understand the knowledge and skills of students, develop them personally and identify their changing potential.
2. Orientation to Practice: The principles of self-expression and learning are central to orientation to practice in the dual education system. It gives the professional personnel the opportunity to test their new knowledge and skills in practice, learn and teach them to students.

3. Distance education: Studying the pedagogical technologies and principles of distance education with the help of technologies, using these technologies and teaching them to specialists is the main part of the dual education system.

4. Individual completion: training of specialist personnel based on individual characteristics and needs of students. This requires the selection of teaching methods that are suitable for each student and the provision of special advice during their learning.

These foundations are an important part of the training of specialist personnel in the dual education system and are essential for students to have the best quality of education.

Conclusion: The discipline established in educational institutions ensures the cohesion of the team of educational institutions, the smooth running of the internal life and activities of the educational institution. Discipline requires students to act in solidarity, to fight together for the benefit of the school, and the management and authorized student bodies, its members, to interpret the students correctly and to fulfill them. In conclusion, I would like to emphasize once again that guiding our youth to the right profession is one of the most important tasks. It is a law that does not require proof that a person can bring great benefits to his family and society by choosing the right profession.

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9. Training of expert personnel in the educational system
10. Nusratov Anvar Nematjonovich
11. Associate Professor of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute
12. Isoqova Shaxnoza Shuxrat qizi
13. Master's student of the 1st stage of pedagogy and
14. psychology at the International
15. University of Asia